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NET-Fuels deliverable report

D2.1 - Report on feedstock characterisation

Dissemination Level: Public

NET- Fuels | INCREASING BIOMASS CONVERSION EFFICIENCY TO CARBON-NEGATIVE SUSTAINABLE BIOFUELS BY COMBINATION OF THERMOCHEMICAL AND BIO-ELECTROCHEMICAL PROCESSES

HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-09 | GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER: 101083780

Deliverable D2.1: Report on feedstock characterisation

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	x
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

Document Type		
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	x
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
DMP	Data management plan	
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	
SECURITY	Deliverables related to security issues	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	

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General Information

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NET-Fuels consortium

Short	Beneficiary	Role
UNIBO	Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna	CO
FRA	Fraunhofer UMSICHT	BEN
LEITAT	Acondicionamiento Tarrasense (LEITAT)	BEN
SUT	Silesian University of Technology	BEN
ITHAKA	Ithaka Institute	BEN
REACH	REACH Innovation	BEN
WRG	WRG Europe	AP

CO...Coordinator, BEN...Beneficiary, AP...Associated Partner

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Executive Summary

This report on feedstock characterisation as deliverable D2.1 is a comprehensive characterization of representative samples of the feedstock supplied to FRA. A wide range of relevant feedstock was covered from woody biomass residues over prunings to residues from agriculture and livestock farming. Pre-treatment procedures and results are reported as undertaken in Task 2.1.

Task 2.1 is the first task in work package WP2, which entails the thermo-chemical conversion of biogenic residues and supply of CO₂ and biochar.

This report covers WP specific objective O2.1 to test different biogenic residues as feedstock for production of CO₂-negative fuels.

1 Introduction

This report provides results to the data sets as outlined in the grant agreement

2 Task 2.1 organization, roles and responsibilities

Table 1: Organisation, roles and responsibilities for task T2.1

Organization, roles and responsibilities			
Partner	FRA	ITHAKA	type
Lead	X		organization
deliverable	X		role
Obligatory			
Feedstock definition	X		role
Main feedstock supply		X	role
Main feedstock receipt	X		responsibility
Feedstock processing	X		role
Feedstock analysis	X		role
Additional			
Feedstock analysis	X		Responsibility
Sample feedstock supply 1kg each to SUT	X		Role

2.1 Contacts

Table 2: Contacts for the Task T2.1

Contacts			
Partner	Primary (To)	Secondary (CC)	Role
FRA	Martin Meiller martin.meiller@umsicht.fraunhofer.de	christian.groves@umsicht.fraunhofer.de christopher.kick@umsicht.fraunhofer.de johannes.neidel@umsicht.fraunhofer.de	Lead
ITHAKA	Nikolas Hagemann hagemann@ithaka-institut.org		Participant
SUT	Andrzej Szlęk andrzej.szlek@polsl.pl		Recipient
UNIBO	Ilaria Carbone ilaria.carbone2@unibo.it		Coordinator

2.2 Dependencies

Table 3: Dependencies of the task T2.1

Dependencies			
Task	Dependent on	Month	Comment
T 2.1. Feedstock supply, pre-treatment and characterization (Lead Fraunhofer)	None	None	This report
T 2.2. Modelling and design of oxyfuel combustion and heat transfer to TCR (Lead SUT)	Feedstock samples for own analysis	Not defined; report first due in M24 so October 2024.	Not defined as a requirement in D1.1 project management plan.
T 2.3. Thermo-chemical conversion and oxyfuel combustion tests (Lead Fraunhofer)	Feedstock analysis from T2.1	M6-M12 (until October 2023).	Pilot plant of T2.3 will only operate after Report is submitted; results are needed for detailed design.
T 2.4. TCR-char characterization and evaluation of potential application in the soil as amendment and carbon sink (Lead ITAKA)	TCR char production	M12 (October 2023)	Biochar from TCR available.

2.3 Task description

This deliverable reports on Task 2.1: Feedstock supply, pre-treatment and characterization (FRA) (M1-M12); With FRA as the lead and ITHAKA as a participant, who provides feedstock supply.

The project examines the use of three different biogenic residues from agriculture and forestry. These are digestate from anaerobic digestion of manure and corn silage, calamity wood and prunings. In addition, additional feedstocks have been examined to provide additional context and broaden the perspective with regards to potential applications of the TCR pyrolysis technology. The representative analysis samples come from large quantities of feedstock as provided from the supplier network available to FRA and ITHAKA. Concurrently, the three main feedstocks have been pyrolyzed at FRA in the TCR30 pyrolysis plant.

2.4 Analysis purpose

This dataset's purpose is to provide input for Task 2.4 TCR-char characterization and evaluation of potential application in the soil as amendment and carbon sink. It allows to interpret the TCR-char characterization with regard to the fate of different element during the thermochemical conversion during the TCR process. The input is needed to be able to characterize feedstocks for the C-sink assessment of the NET-Fuel approach.

The analyses are required to enable identification of any differences relevant to the feedstock used in this project at a later stage. It is also needed to assess variability within a given feedstock definition (e.g., "pruning") with alternatives. This requires specific analyses to assess the feedstock evaluated for this project. Additionally, there is similar, existing data for other feedstocks (different sample materials). Existing data has also been reused, since it may be useful to complement the data gained from the analyses used for the project.

3 Feedstock descriptions

Three different biogenic residues from agriculture and forestry are foreseen to be treated in the NET-Fuels project. Digestate is representative of secondary biomasses derived from annual crops (maize, other cereals and leguminous plants used as animal feed) with high water and low lignin content. Calamity wood and wine prunings are examples of lignocellulosic biomasses from different European countries. Pruning is seasonal while digestate is essentially produced continuously throughout the year.

3.1 Digestate as an example for residues from agriculture and livestock farming

Digestate obtained from the anaerobic digestion of manure and maize silage is an important agricultural residual material with great potential. Here, above all, it must be ensured that nutrients are kept in the cycle. Digestate is pretreated by first separating the solid and liquid phases. The liquid phase with a high content of soluble nutrients is for digestate, the pre-treatment will be more complex: first a solid-liquid separation will take place. It is common practice for the liquid phase with high content of soluble nutrients to be directly applied to fields as a commercial fertilizer. There is potential for mixing the separated liquid phase with biochar before soil application. The solid phase is dried to a water content of below 20 percent and subsequently pelletized for the thermo-chemical conversion trials. In ANNEX I – BGK certificate digestate pellets test report more properties and contents are shown. Bundesgütegemeinschaft Kompost (BGK) is a German NGO that offers, among other, third-party certified quality assurance for digestates to be used as a fertilizer or soil amendment. Analysis was conducted according to their guidelines. The results given in the feedstock analysis is from digestate tested recently in October 2023. This digestate was used to produce the biochar sent to ITHAKA. This is assumed to have a similar composition as that given in the BGK certificate for test pellets taken in October 2017 at before delivery.

3.2 Calamity wood as an example for residues from forestry and wood biomass

In Central Europe, the effects of climate change on forest stands are becoming apparent. Damages caused by drought, bark beetle infestation and storms have led to the accumulation of large quantities of calamity wood, i.e. wood that is not suitable for the initially intended material use. Calamity wood usually must be removed from the forest to reduce the risk of ongoing bark beetle infestation. Similar feedstocks to calamity wood are pretreated by chipping and drying. Wine prunings have a similar composition as calamity wood. Pollard willow wood and burl wood are also given as similar feedstocks as calamity wood. The pretreatment of calamity wood is chipping, drying and pelletizing.

3.3 Prunings as an example for residues from forestry and wood biomass

Offcuts from vineyards and orchards regularly accumulate in large quantities, especially in Southern Europe. The pretreatment of prunings is chipping, drying and pelletizing.

3.4 Low lignin biomass as an example for residues from agriculture

Olive pressing residue, olive stones and hops extraction residues are also given as examples of other residues available from European agriculture. Olive pressing residue was dried and pelletized. The pellets were then dried once more at 75 °C for 16 hours. Olive stones were only dried at atmospheric conditions and subsequently pelletized.

4 Physical appearance of the feedstock

The physical appearance is shown in feedstock pictures as given in Table 4.

Table 4: Feedstock pictures during preparation

Feedstock pictures during preparation		
Test ID	Material	Image
TCR30 V69	Digestate	below
Test ID	Material	Images
TCR30 V70	Wine prunings	below

Test ID	Material	Images
TCR30 V72	Hops extraction residues	below

Test ID	Material	Images
TCR2 V120	Olive pressing residue	below

Test ID	Material	Images
TCR2 V127	Olive stones	below

Test ID	Material	Images
TCR2 V134	Pollard willow wood	below

Test ID	Material	Images
TCR2 V136	Burl wood	below

5 Methods

The methods are given in the form of tables, which correspond to the feedstock results.

5.1 Elemental analysis method

Table 5: Methods of the elemental analysis of dry samples

Methods of the elemental analysis of dry samples							
Test ID	Material	N [%]	C [%]	H [%]	S [%]	O [%]	Sum
BGK Certificate	Digestate	BGK e.V. Methodenbuch ("Method book")					
TCR30 V69	Digestate	DIN 51732: 2014-07 (Dry, Ma.-%)		DIN 51724-3: 2012-07 (Dry, Ma.-%)		DIN 51733: 2016-04 (Dry, Ma.-%)	
TCR30 V70	Wine prunings	DIN EN ISO 16948:2015-09 (Dry, Ma.-%)		DIN EN ISO 16994:2016-12 (Dry, Ma.-%)		DIN EN ISO 16993: 2016-11 (Dry, Ma.-%)	
TCR30 V72	Hops extraction residues						
TCR2 V120	Olive pressing residue	based on DIN EN ISO 16948:2015-09 (Dry, Ma.-%), according to CHNS analyser "vario MACRO cube" ¹		according to CHNS analyser "vario MACRO cube"		based on DIN 51733: 2016-04 (Dry, Ma.-%)	
TCR2 V127	Olive stones						
TCR2 V134	Pollard willow wood						
TCR2 V136	Burl wood						

The nitrogen, carbon, and hydrogen values for the elemental analysis of digestate have been measured according to DIN 51732: 2014-07, Testing of solid mineral fuels - Determination of total carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen - Instrumental methods and not DIN EN ISO 16948:2015-09, Solid biofuels - Determination of total content of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen. This is due to the testing standards selected for sewage sludge based on previous analyses and the assumption that digestate is comparable to sewage sludge.

The sulphur values for the elemental analysis of digestate have been measured according to DIN 51724-3:2012-07, Solid mineral fuels - Determination of sulfur content - Part 3: Instrumental methods and not DIN EN ISO 16994:2016-12, Solid biofuels - Determination of total content of sulfur and chlorine. This is also due to the testing standards selected for sewage sludge based on previous analyses and the assumption that digestate is comparable to sewage sludge.

¹ vario MACRO cube CHNS macro analyser from Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH, Langenselbold, Germany

5.2 X-Ray fluorescence (XRF) elemental analysis method

Trace elements are measured with an X-Ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis on samples of the wet feedstocks, dry feedstocks, ash and TCR char after processing in the TCR pyrolysis reactor and post reformer. This form of measurement deviates significantly from the standard DIN EN 15411:2011-11.

Feed (moist) in given in the XRF elemental analysis results in Table 8 and Table 9 refer to feedstock in the undried state, commonly described in the standards used as “as received”. This deviates from the standard practice of measurement in the dried state. The values can be converted using the formulae given in DIN EN ISO 16993:2016-11 to the dry state.

The char was produced in the TCR2 pyrolysis reactor at the temperatures of 320°C, 420°C and 450°C for the different stages, and in the post reformer at a temperature of 750°C.

The ash was prepared by heating the as received feedstock in an oven at 550°C for 24 hours.

The equipment used for the XRF analysis was the S1 TITAN 600-800 model manufactured by Bruker Elemental. This is a portable handheld XRF analysis device. It emits ionizing radiation generated by a miniature X-ray tube (Bruker, undated).

This was calibrated according to the Restricted Materials Calibration (document P/N: 730.0091), This also defines the smallest measurement possible. The manufacturer Bruker gives the smallest measurement as by the Limit of Detection (LOD). Some LODs may be represented by artificial thresholds, which prevent the measurement of false positives. The LOD is defined with a three-sigma confidence level of 99.7 percent. This analyses dual phases for 180 seconds (Bruker 2014).

5.3 Feedstock physical-chemical analysis method

Table 6: Methods of the physical-chemical analysis

Methods of the physical-chemical analysis of the feedstock								
Test ID	Material	Dry residue [%]	Water content [%]	Loss on ignition [%]	Ash content [%]	Bulk density [kg/m ³]	Calorific value [MJ/kg]	Location
BGK certificate	Digestate	BGK method book	DIN EN ISO 16993: 2016-11	-	-	BGK method book	-	BGK Cologne
TCR30 V69	Digestate	DIN EN ISO 16993: 2016-11	DIN EN 12880 (S2a): 2001-02 (original, Ma.-%)	DIN EN ISO 16993: 2016-11	DIN 51719: 1997-07 (815°C, dry, Ma.-%)	BGK e.V.: 9/2006, Ch. II, A4 (Ma.-%)	DIN EN 15170: 2009-05 (const. vol., dry)	Eurofins Umwelt-Ost GmbH, Bobritsch-Hilbersdorf
TCR30 V70	Wine prunings	DIN EN ISO 16993: 2016-11	DIN EN ISO 18134-3 (original, Ma.-%)	DIN EN ISO 18122 (550°C, dry, Ma.-%)	DIN EN ISO 18122 (550°C, dry, Ma.-%)	DIN EN ISO 17828: 2016-05 (Ma.-%)	DIN EN ISO 18125: 2017-08 (const. vol., dry)	
TCR30 V72	Hops extraction residues							
TCR2 V120	Olive pressing residue	based on DIN EN ISO 18134-3 Muffle furnace (original, Ma.-%)	based on DIN EN ISO 16993: 2016-11	based on DIN EN ISO 18122 (550°C, dry, Ma.-%)	based on DIN EN ISO 18122 (550°C, dry, Ma.-%)	settling and weighing of 1000 ml samples	IKA C2000 basic calorimeter ² , Bomb calorimeter, based on DIN 51900	Fraunhofer UMSICHT Sulzbach-Rosenberg
TCR2 V127	Olive stones							
TCR2 V134	Pollard willow wood							
TCR2 V136	Burl wood							

² IKA C2000 basic calorimeter from IKA-Werke GmbH & CO. KG, Staufen, Germany

6 Results

The results are given in the form of tables, which best compare the feedstock characteristics.

6.1 Elemental analysis results

Table 7: Results of the elemental analysis of dry samples

Results of the elemental analysis of dry samples								
Test ID	Material	N [%] ³	C [%]	H [%]	S [%]	Ash ⁴ [%]	O ⁵ [%]	Sum [%]
BGK Certificate	Digestate	2.0	-	-	0.36	-	-	-
TCR30 V69	Digestate	1.8	42.9	4.7	0.51	14.7	35.4	100.0
TCR30 V70	Wine prunings	0.9	47.9	5.5	0.05	4.5	41.1	100.0
TCR30 V72	Hops extraction residues	4.1	46.1	5.3	0.25	10.1	34.1	100.0
TCR2 V120	Olive pressing residue	1.6	48.0	7.1	0.15	9.0	34.1	100.0
TCR2 V127	Olive stones	0.2	48.7	7.1	0.01	1.1	42.9	100.0
TCR2 V134	Pollard willow wood	0.5	46.7	6.9	0.03	2.5	43.4	100.0
TCR2 V136	Burl wood	1.1	44.4	6.7	0.10	5.3	42.4	100.0

The results for the BGK certificate are from ANNEX I – BGK certificate digestate pellets test report.

The results for the test TCR 30 V69 are from ANNEX II – TCR30 V69 digestate pellets test report.

The results for the tests TCR30 V70 and TCR30 V72 are from ANNEX III – TCR30 V70 wine prunings and TCR30 V72 hops extraction residues pellets report.

6.2 XRF elemental analysis results

The XRF elemental analysis results show the main and trace element compositions (mass %, based on XRF analysis) of feedstock (“Feed”), TCR char produced on TCR2, and ash of the respective material.

The results are given on the following page.

³ Mass percent.

⁴ Entries for ash [%] are carried over from Table 11: Results of the physical-chemical analysis.

⁵ Calculated as O [%] = 1 – N – C – H – S – O – Ash.

Table 8: Main and trace element compositions of TCR2 feedstock, produced char, and ash

Main and trace element compositions of TCR2 feedstock, produced char, and ash									
Test	TCR2 V120			TCR2 V127			TCR2 V134		
Material	Olive pressing residue			Olive stones			Pollard willow wood		
Condition	Feed (moist)	Char	Ash	Feed (moist)	Char	Ash	Feed (moist)	Char	Ash
Element Compound	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)
Al	NA	5.91	20.12	NA	NA	19.95	NA	NA	14.91
SiO ₂	NA	2.15	19.97	NA	NA	13.92	NA	NA	8.26
Cl	0.18	1.66	4.57	0.01	0.07	3.44	<LOD	0.11	1.21
Ca	0.16	1.35	5.52	0.04	0.20	5.58	0.75	0.49	11.58
Ti	<LOD	0.01	0.03	<LOD	<LOD	0.21	<LOD	<LOD	0.04
V	NA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	NA	NA	NA	NA	<LOD
Cr	0.00	0.00	0.01	<LOD	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01
Mn	<LOD	NA	0.01	<LOD	<LOD	0.02	<LOD	0.00	0.04
Fe	0.02	0.16	0.35	0.00	0.04	1.62	0.01	0.06	0.67
Co	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Ni	<LOD	NA	NA	<LOD	<LOD	NA	<LOD	<LOD	NA
Cu	0.00	0.01	0.02	<LOD	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01
Zn	0.00	0.01	0.02	<LOD	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.07
As	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Se	<LOD	NA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0.00	0.00	<LOD
Br	0.00	0.00	0.01	<LOD	0.00	0.00	<LOD	0.00	0.00
Sr	NA	NA	0.02	NA	NA	0.01	NA	NA	0.02
Zr	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0.01	NA	NA	NA
Mo	NA	<LOD	<LOD	NA	NA	<LOD	NA	NA	<LOD
Pd	NA	NA	<LOD	NA	NA	<LOD	NA	NA	<LOD
Ag	NA	0.01	0.01	NA	NA	0.01	NA	NA	0.01
Cd	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	NA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Sn	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Sb	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Ba	<LOD	0.01	0.01	<LOD	<LOD	0.01	<LOD	<LOD	0.01
Hf	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	<LOD	NA	NA	<LOD
Ta	NA	<LOD	<LOD	NA	NA	<LOD	NA	NA	<LOD
W	NA	<LOD	<LOD	NA	NA	<LOD	NA	NA	<LOD
Pt	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	<LOD	NA	NA	<LOD
Au	NA	0.03	0.03	NA	NA	0.03	NA	NA	0.02
Hg	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Pb	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Bi	NA	<LOD	<LOD	NA	NA	<LOD	NA	NA	NA

values in percent (%), assumed to be mass percent.

NA = value not available

<LOD = below limit of detection

Cells have been greyed out where the value is either 0.00 %, NA or <LOD to aid visualization.

Table 9: Main and trace element compositions of TCR30 feedstock and ash

Main and trace element compositions of TCR30 feedstock and ash								
Test	TCR30 V69		TCR30 V70		Undeclared		TCR30 V72	
Material	Digestate		Wine prunings		Wood pellets		Hops extraction residues	
Condition	Feed (moist)	Ash	Feed (moist)	Ash	Feed (moist)	Ash	Feed (moist)	Ash
Element Compound	[%]	[%]	[%]	[%]	[%]	[%]	[%]	[%]
Al	NA	8.27	NA	14.15	NA	8.54	NA	21.25
SiO ₂	NA	19.34	NA	12.99	NA	5.46	NA	10.71
Cl	0.25	4.91	0.01	0.18	0.00	<LOD	0.15	3.15
Ca	0.80	5.94	0.61	8.85	0.28	17.08	0.20	5.31
Ti	<LOD	0.03	<LOD	0.04	<LOD	0.27	<LOD	0.01
V	NA	NA	<LOD	NA	<LOD	NA	NA	<LOD
Cr	0.00	0.00	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	0.04	0.00	0.00
Mn	0.02	0.17	0.01	0.09	0.02	0.93	0.01	0.04
Fe	0.13	1.06	0.03	0.50	0.01	0.85	0.01	0.11
Co	NA	NA	NA	<LOD	NA	<LOD	NA	NA
Ni	<LOD	NA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	NA	<LOD	NA
Cu	0.00	0.02	<LOD	0.01	<LOD	0.01	0.00	0.03
Zn	0.01	0.14	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.14	0.00	0.03
As	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Se	<LOD	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	<LOD	NA	<LOD	<LOD
Br	0.00	0.00	0.00	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0.00	0.01
Sr	NA	0.02	NA	0.01	NA	0.01	NA	NA
Zr	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Mo	NA	<LOD	NA	<LOD	NA	<LOD	NA	<LOD
Pd	NA	<LOD	NA	<LOD	NA	NA	NA	<LOD
Ag	NA	0.01	NA	0.01	NA	0.01	NA	0.01
Cd	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Sn	0.00	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0.00	<LOD
Sb	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Ba	<LOD	0.01	<LOD	0.01	<LOD	0.02	<LOD	0.01
Hf	NA	<LOD	NA	<LOD	NA	<LOD	NA	NA
Ta	NA	<LOD	NA	<LOD	NA	NA	NA	<LOD
W	NA	<LOD	NA	<LOD	NA	<LOD	NA	<LOD
Pt	NA	<LOD	NA	NA	NA	<LOD	NA	NA
Au	NA	0.04	NA	0.02	NA	0.02	NA	0.03
Hg	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Pb	0.00	0.01	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0.00	<LOD	<LOD
Bi	NA	<LOD	NA	<LOD	NA	<LOD	NA	<LOD

values in percent (%), assumed to be mass percent.

NA = value not available

<LOD = below limit of detection

Cells have been greyed out where the value is either 0.00 %, NA or <LOD to aid visualization.

6.3 Feedstock physical-chemical analysis results

In the table below, corrections of calorific values for sulphur and nitrogen content are made according to DIN 51900. The adapted higher heating value is insignificantly different to the higher heating valve of the calorimeter when the repeatability limits, reproducibility limits and the ranges are considered. For the results of TCR2 V127 and TCR2 V136, the range of the results are significantly greater than both the repeatability limit and the reproducibility limit.

The higher heating value calorimeter refers to the measured higher heating value from the instrumentation before accounting for changes in heating value due to the oxidation of nitrogen and sulphur. The Chlorine value is from the elemental analysis as given in Table 8 and does not need to be considered when it is below 1 percent. The Florine value has not been measured.

Table 10: Corrections of calorific values for sulphur and nitrogen content

Corrections of calorific values for sulphur and nitrogen content										
Test ID	-		TCR2 V120		TCR2 V127		TCR2 V134		TCR2 V136	
Material	-		Olive pressing residue		Olive stones		Pollard willow wood		Burl wood	
Nitrogen	N	[%]	1.61		0.19		0.52		1.12	
Sulphur	S	[%]	0.15		0.01		0.03		0.10	
Florine	F	[%]	-		-		-		-	
Chlorine	Cl	[%]	0.18		0.01		-		-	
Higher heating value calorimeter	HHV_{calo.}	kJ/kg	18679	18999	19491	13168	18175	18194	17732	17834
N [%] x 42.96	Q_N	kJ/kg	69.17	69.17	8.162	8.162	22.34	22.34	48.12	48.12
S [%] x 94.1	Q_S	kJ/kg	14.1	14.1	0.941	0.941	2.82	2.82	9.41	9.41
F [%] x 32.40	Q_F	kJ/kg	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cl [%] x 20.84	Q_{Cl}	kJ/kg	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Difference		kJ/kg	83	83	9	9	25	25	58	58
Higher heating value HHV, adapted (not considered)	HHV	kJ/kg	18596	18916	19482	13159	18150	18169	17674	17776
Repeatability limit		kJ/kg	300 (solid derived fuels)							
Reproducibility limit		kJ/kg	1400 (solid derived fuels)							
Range		kJ/kg	320		6323		19		102	
Mean average		kJ/kg	18756		16320		18159		17725	
Higher heating value HHV, constant volume	HHV	MJ/kg	18.8		16		18.2		17.7	

Table 11: Results of the physical-chemical analysis of the feedstock

Results of the physical-chemical analysis of the feedstock								
Test ID	Material	Equivalent feedstock	Dry residue [%]	Water content [%]	Loss on ignition [%]	Ash content [%]	Bulk density [kg/m ³]	Calorific value [MJ/kg]
BGK certificate	Digestate	Digestate	94.1	5.9	-	-	674	-
TCR30 V69	Digestate	Digestate	87.3	12.7	85.3	14.7	700	17.25
TCR30 V70	Wine prunings	Wine prunings	92.1	7.9	95.5	4.5	680	19.0
TCR30 V72	Hops extraction residues	Wine prunings	88.8	11.2	89.9	10.1	611	18.3
TCR2 V120	Olive pressing residue	Wine prunings	98.55	1.45	90.98	9.02	666.75	18.8
TCR2 V127	Olive stones	Wine prunings	93.30	6.70	98.94	1.06	685.75	16
TCR2 V134	Pollard willow wood	Calamity wood	93.29	6.71	97.52	2.48	714.40	18.2
TCR2 V136	Burl wood	Calamity wood	90.99	9.01	94.71	5.29	616.65	17.7

For the BGK Certificate, values are taken from ANNEX I – BGK certificate digestate pellets test report.

For TCR30 V69, values are taken from ANNEX II – TCR30 V69 digestate pellets test report.

For TCR30 V70 and TCR30 V72, values are taken from ANNEX III – TCR30 V70 wine prunings and TCR30 V72 hops extraction residues pellets report.

For TCR2 V120, TCR2 V127 and TCR2 V136, the corrected calorific values from Table 10 are used.

[%] refers to mass percent.

The calorific value is Higher heating value HHV, measured at constant volume.

ANNEX I – BGK certificate digestate pellets test report

The report is labelled as attachment LW to PZ-No.: 8559-151535-02: Pellets (Digestate product solid 2 of the German company NawaRo in Steinfurt, Germany) (BGK-No.: 8559) (BGK 2017). It has certification according to RAL-GZ 246 from the German third party institute “RAL Deutsches Institut für Gütesicherung und Kennzeichnung e.V.”

Regulatory definitions of the product are that it is regulated as a fertilizer and hygienically non-hazardous. It is certified as the product NawaRo Digestate product as overseen by the 3rd party inspection test RAL-GZ 246. It has external supervision from the BGK (Bundesgütegemeinschaft Kompost e.V.). It is also suitable for use in a protected groundwater zone class III.

The digestate is defined as an organic matter NPK (Nitrogen, Phosphorous and Potassium) fertilizer, given as 1.91 -4.14-1.78 as N-P-K with Micronutrients, as defined in Table 14. It is made with plant-based substances and byproducts of animal origin. It yields constituents as given in Table 12 und properties as given in Table 13.

The conversion rate of undried mass to dried mass is 0.94. The conversion rate from dried mass to undried mass is 1.06. The conversion rate of volume in m³ to mass in tonnes (t) is 0.67. The conversion rate of mass in tonnes (t) to volume in m³ is 1.48.

Table 12: Digestate properties and contents in the undried mass

Digestate properties and contents in the undried mass			
Constituent compounds	Compound	kg/t	kg/m ³
Total nitrogen content	N	19.20	12.94
Nitrogen soluble in CaCl ₂	N	0.54	0.36
Organic nitrogen	N	18.66	12.58
Total phosphate	P ₂ O ₅	41.40	27.91
Total potassium oxide	K ₂ O	17.88	12.05
Total magnesium oxide	MgO	21.64	14.59
Total sulphur	S	3.39	2.28
Alkaline active substances	CaO	20.04	13.51

Table 13: Undried digestate properties

Undried digestate properties		
Property	Unit	Value
pH value	-	7.2
Salt content	gram / litre	16
Organic substance	kg/t	696
humus-C	kg/t	141
bulk density	kg/m ³	674
dry mass	%	94.1
Nitrogen from commercial fertilizer of animal origin	kg/t undried mass	1.5

Table 14: Digestate constituents

Digestate constituents				
Constituent	Compound	Unit	undried mass	dry mass
Plant nutrients				
Total nitrogen content	N	%	1.920	2.04
Available nitrogen content	N	%	0.05	-
Total phosphate	P ₂ O ₅	%	4.140	4.40
Total potassium oxide	K ₂ O	%	1.788	1.90
Total magnesium oxide	MgO	%	2.164	2.30
Sulphur	S	%	0.339	0.36
Copper	Cu	mg/kg	-	51.0
Zinc	Zn	mg/kg	-	210
Ammonium CaCl ₂ soluble	NH ₄ -N	mg/l	350	-
Nitrate CaCl ₂ soluble	NO ₃ -N	mg/l	14	-
Soil improvement				
Organic substance	-	%	-	74.0
Alkaline active components	CaO	%	2.004	2.13
Physical parameters				
degree of fermentation	organic acids	mg/l	74	-
Heavy metals				
Lead	Pb	mg/kg	-	< 1.00
Cadmium	Cd	mg/kg	-	0.20
Chrome	Cr	mg/kg	-	9.10
Nickel	Ni	mg/kg	-	7.50
Mercury	Hg	mg/kg	-	0.02

Table 15: Further data for fertilizer calculation

Further data for fertilizer calculation				
Constituent	Compound	%	kg/t	kg/m ³
Total nitrogen	N	1.92	19.2	12.9
Soluble nitrogen	N	0.05	0.54	0.36
Organic nitrogen	N	1.87	18.7	12.6
Total phosphate	P ₂ O ₅	4.14	41.4	27.9
Total potassium oxide	K ₂ O	1.79	17.9	12.1
Total magnesium oxide	MgO	2.16	21.6	14.6
Alkaline active components	CaO	2.00	20.0	13.5
Organic matter	-	69.6	696	469
Humus-C	-	14.1	141	95.3

The original certificate and the machine translation of the certificate into English with deepL pro are given on the following 6 pages.

RAL Prüfzeugnis

RAL-GZ 246 PZ-Nr.: 8559-151535-02

Pellets

RAL-Gütesicherung
Nawaro-Gärprodukt
Chargenuntersuchung
Seite 1 von 3Anlage Steinfurt
(BGK-Nr.: 8559)
Charge: Pellets
Probenahme am 04.10.2017

Rechtsbestimmungen:

- Düngemittelverordnung
- Organischer NPK-Dünger
- hygienisch unbedenklich (§ 5 Düngemittelverordnung)

Regelwerke:

- NawaRo-Gärprodukt fest (Überwachungsverfahren RAL-GZ 246)
- Fremdüberwachung der BGK
- Grundwasserschutzgebiete⁵⁾ (geeignet für WSZ III)

Zeichengrundlage unter
www.gz-nawaro-gaerprodukt.de

Die Einhaltung der jeweiligen Norm wird mit einem Häkchen ausgewiesen.

Warendeklaration der RAL-Gütesicherung¹⁾

Kennzeichnung

gemäß Düngemittelverordnung

Organischer NPK-Dünger 1,91-4,14-1,78 mit Spurennährstoffen
unter Verwendung von pflanzlichen Stoffen, tierischen Nebenprodukten1,91 % N Gesamtstickstoff
0,05 % N verfügbarer Stickstoff
4,14 % P₂O₅ Gesamtphosphat
1,78 % K₂O Gesamtkaliumoxid
0,0197 % Zn Gesamtzink**Nettomasse und ggf. Volumen: siehe Lieferschein**
Inverkehrbringer:
Bioenergie Steinfurt GmbH & Co. KG
Hollich 81a
48565 Steinfurt

Ausgangsstoffe:

Pflanzliche Stoffe aus der Landwirtschaft (66%), Gülle.

Hinweise zur Lagerung:

Lagerung nur in geeigneten und zugelassenen Behältern/Anlagen unter Berücksichtigung anderer Rechtsbestimmungen. Vor der Entnahme ausreichend durchmischen.

Hinweise zur Anwendung:

Hinweise zur sachgerechten Anwendung siehe Anlage LW. Die Empfehlungen der amtlichen Beratung sind vorrangig zu berücksichtigen.

Anwendungsvorgaben:

Bei Anwendung dieses Düngemittels sind die Sperrfristen der Düngeverordnung in den Wintermonaten zu beachten.
[ListeNebenbestandteile]

Sonstige Angaben:

Hygieneanforderungen geprüft und eingehalten.
Frei von keimfähigen Samen und austriebfähigen PflanzenteilenDüngewert²⁾ 38,81 €/t 26,16 €/m³
Humuswert³⁾ 24,03 €/t 16,20 €/m³

Eigenschaften und Inhaltsstoffe in der Frischmasse

	kg/t	kg/m ³
Stickstoff gesamt (N)	19,20	12,94
Stickstoff CaCl ₂ -löslich (N)	0,54	0,36
Stickstoff organisch (N)	18,66	12,58
Phosphat gesamt (P ₂ O ₅)	41,40	27,91
Kaliumoxid gesamt (K ₂ O)	17,88	12,05
Magnesiumoxid ges.(MgO)	21,64	14,59
Schwefel gesamt (S)	3,39	2,28
Basisch wirksame Stoffe (CaO)	20,04	13,51
pH-Wert		7,2
Salzgehalt		16 g/l
Organische Substanz		696 kg/t
Humus-C		141 kg/t
Rohdichte		674 kg/m ³
Trockenmasse		94,1 %
Stickstoff aus Wirtschaftsdünger tierischer Herkunft		1,5 kg/tFM

Erzeugnis unterliegt der RAL-Gütesicherung Nawaro-Gärprodukt (RAL-GZ 246). Das Zeugnis wurde elektronisch erstellt. Es gilt ohne Unterschrift.

Bundesgütegemeinschaft
Kompost e.V.
Träger der regelmäßigen Güteüberwachung gemäß §11 Abs. 3 BioAbfV.

Köln, den 19.12.2017

1) bei der Abgabe des Erzeugnisses verbindliche Warendeklaration der RAL-Gütesicherung. 2) gemäß aktuellem Marktwert, ermittelt über äquivalente Kosten mineralischer Düngung nach Landhandelspreisen (Juli - Sep. 2017) ohne MwSt. (0,63 €/kg N im Anwendungsjahr (N-löslich zzgl. 5% von N-organisch); 0,63 €/kg P₂O₅; 0,57 €/kg K₂O; 0,08 €/kg CaO). 4) Der Wert von Humus-C beträgt 0,17 €/kg Humus-C (Kalkuliert auf Basis eines Strohpreises von 72,50 Euro/t). 5) Ausgewiesen auf Grundlage der DVGW-BGK-Information vom 19.6.2013

Figure 1: BGK certificate digestate pellets test report; original in German, page 1 of 3

RAL-GZ 246

Untersuchungsbericht

PZ-Nr.: 8559-151535-02

Pellets

Steinfurt
(BGK-Nr.: 8559)
Seite 2 von 3Charge: Pellets
Probenahme am 04.10.2017
Prüflabor BGK-Nr.: 46
Tgb-Nr.: 17-156713-02

Allgemeine Angaben

Auftraggeber / -in: Bioenergie Steinfurt GmbH & Co. KG

Probennehmer / -in: Christian Winter
(BGK-Nr.: 674) WESSLING Laboratorien GmbHPrüflabor: WESSLING GmbH
(BGK-Nr.: 46) 48341 Altenberge
Laborverantwortlicher: Herr WellermannProbenahmedatum: 04.10.2017
Probeneingang im Labor: 04.10.2017

Beprobtes Erzeugnis: NawaRo-Gärprodukt fest 2

Produktionsmonat: Oktober
Charge: PelletsProzessüberwachung geprüft, nicht beanstandet

Einsatzstoffe¹⁾

Anteil	Bezeichnung
62%	K1 Silomais (Ganzpflanze)
17%	D1 Rindergülle
17%	D2 Schweinegülle
2,0%	K4 Getreide (Korn)
2,0%	K3 Getreide (Ganzpflanze)

Hilfsstoffe

¹⁾ Einsatzstoffe gemäß Liste zulässiger Einsatzstoffe für die Herstellung gütegesicherter NawaRo-Gärprodukte der BGK (Dok. 246-007-1)

Bemerkung Probennehmer / -in:

Bemerkung Prüflabor:

Die Probenahme und Untersuchung wurde gemäß dem Methodenbuch der BGK e.V. durchgeführt.

Altenberge, den 19.12.2017

Analysenergebnisse

Parameter Wert Einheit

Pflanzennährstoffe

Stickstoff, gesamt (N)	2,04	% TM
Phosphat, gesamt (P ₂ O ₅)	4,40	% TM
Kaliumoxid, gesamt (K ₂ O)	1,90	% TM
Magnesiumoxid, gesamt (MgO)	2,30	% TM
Schwefel (S)	0,36	% TM
Kupfer (Cu)	51,0	mg/kg TM
Zink (Zn)	210	mg/kg TM
Ammonium CaCl ₂ -löslich (NH ₄ -N)	350	mg/l FM
Nitrat CaCl ₂ -löslich (NO ₃ -N)	14	mg/l FM

Bodenverbesserung

Organische Substanz	74,0	% TM
Basisch wirks. Bestandteile (CaO)	2,13	% TM

Physikalische Parameter

Rohdichte	674	g/l
Trockenmasse	94,1	% FM
Salzgehalt	16,0	g/l FM
pH-Wert	7,2	
Vergärungsgrad (Organische Säuren)	74	mg/l FM
Fremdstoffe > 2mm gesamt	0,00	% TM
- verformbare Kunststoffe (Folie)	0,00	% TM
- sonstige Fremdstoffe	0,00	% TM
Verunreinigungsgrad (Flächensumme)	n.u.	

Biologische Parameter/Hygiene

Keimfähige Samen / keimf. Pflanzenteile	0	je l FM
Salmonellen	nicht nachweisbar	
Geruchsbonitur	arttypisch unauffällig	

Schwermetalle

Blei (Pb)	< 1,00	mg/kg TM
Cadmium (Cd)	0,20	mg/kg TM
Chrom (Cr)	9,10	mg/kg TM
Nickel (Ni)	7,50	mg/kg TM
Quecksilber (Hg)	0,02	mg/kg TM

Zusätzliche Parameter

Steine > 10mm	< 0,01	% TM
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Figure 2: BGK certificate digestate pellets test report; original in German, page 2 of 3

RAL-GZ 246

Anwendung Landwirtschaft

Anlage LW zum PZ-Nr.: 8559-151535-02

Pellets

(NawaRo-Gärprodukt fest 2)

BGK-Nr.: 8559

Tabelle 1: Daten zur Düngerechnung
(Angaben in der Frischmasse)

Inhaltsstoff	%	kg/t	kg/m ³
Stickstoff gesamt (N)	1,92	19,2	12,9
Stickstoff löslich (N)	0,05	0,54	0,36
Stickstoff organisch (N)	1,87	18,7	12,6
Phosphat gesamt (P ₂ O ₅)	4,14	41,4	27,9
Kaliumoxid gesamt (K ₂ O)	1,79	17,9	12,1
Magnesiumoxid gesamt (MgO)	2,16	21,6	14,6
Bas. wirks. Bestandteile (CaO)	2,00	20,0	13,5
Organische Substanz	69,6	696	469
Humus-C	14,1	141	95,3

Umrechnungsfaktoren Aufwandmenge

Der Umrechnungsfaktor von Frischmasse (FM) in Trockenmasse (TM) beträgt 0,94 und von TM in FM 1,06. Der Umrechnungsfaktor von Volumen (m³) in Masse (t) beträgt 0,67 und von t in m³ FM 1,48.

Tabelle 2: Stickstoffausnutzung nach DüV

(Mindestanrechenbarkeit nach DüV, Angaben in der Frischmasse)

Stickstoff (N)	% von N _{ges}	kg/t	kg/m ³
Anwendungsjahr ¹⁾	30	5,76	3,88
Erstes Folgejahr*	10	1,92	1,29

Phosphat (P ₂ O ₅)	% von P _{ges}	kg/t	kg/m ³
Anwendung in der Fruchtfolge ²⁾	100	41,4	27,9

*nach § 4 Abs. 1 Nr. 5 DüV anzurechnende Folgewirkung.

Tabelle 3: Mittlere Aufwandmengen und Düngewert
(am Beispiel einer dreigliedrigen Fruchtfolge)

	Aufwandmenge (FM)		Düngewert ^{3,6)}	Humuswert ⁴⁾
	t/ha	m ³ /ha		
jährlich	1	2	56	35
in drei Jahren ²⁾	4	6	169	104

Die Tabelle zeigt ein Beispiel für Aufwandmengen zur Versorgung einer dreigliedrigen Fruchtfolge. Dem Beispiel liegt eine mittlere Versorgungsstufe des Bodens und ein jährlicher Bedarf von 60 kg/ha P₂O₅ zugrunde. Im vorliegenden Fall ist Phosphat limitierend. Der Bedarf der Fruchtfolge (180 kg/ha P₂O₅) kann mit 4 t bzw. 6 m³/ha Gärprodukt gedeckt werden.

1) Ermittelte Gehalt an verfügbarem Stickstoff, jedoch mindestens 30% von N-gesamt (DüV Anlage 3). 2) Bei Düngung für die gesamte Fruchtfolge (Grunddüngung) können die jährlichen Aufwandmengen für eine Bedarfsdeckung von 3 Jahren summiert werden. 3) Gemäß aktuellem Marktwert, ermittelt über äquivalente Kosten mineralischer Düngung nach mittleren Landhandelspreisen (Juli - Sep. 2017) ohne MwSt. (0,63 €/kg N-anrechenbar, 0,63 €/kg P₂O₅, 0,57 €/kg K₂O, 0,08 €/kgCaO). 4) Der Wert von Humus-C beträgt 0,17 €/kg Humus-C (Kalkuliert auf Basis eines Strohpreises von 72,50 Euro/t). 5) Abzurufen unter www.kompost.de. 6) Anrechenbarer Stickstoff im Anwendungsjahr (N-löslich zzgl. 5% von N-organisch).

Anrechnung von Nährstoffen und Humus

Stickstoff im Gärprodukt liegt in mineralischer und in organisch gebundener Form vor. Tabelle 2 zeigt die Anrechenbarkeit nach Düngeverordnung (DüV).

Phosphat, Kaliumoxid, Magnesiumoxid sowie basisch wirksame Stoffe sind in der Fruchtfolge zu 100 % anrechenbar. Humus-C ist der im Rahmen der Humusbilanz nach VDLUFA anrechenbare humusproduktionswirksame Kohlenstoff (Humus-C).

Angaben nach Düngeverordnung

Nach DüV handelt es sich um ein Düngemittel

- mit wesentlichem Nährstoffgehalt (gemäß § 2, Nr. 11 DüV, >1,5 % N oder >0,5 % P₂O₅ i.d. TM)
- mit wesentlichem Gehalt an Stickstoff (gemäß § 2 Nr. 11 DüV >1,5% N)

Das Gärprodukt unterliegt der Sperrfrist in den Wintermonaten nach § 6 Abs. 8 DüV. (i.d.R. Ackerland: Ernte der letzten Hauptfrucht bis 31.Januar, Grünland: 1.November bis 31.Januar). Ausnahmen nach § 6 Abs. 9 DüV sind möglich.

Beim Nährstoffvergleich werden die Gesamtgehalte an Stickstoff und Phosphat zu Grunde gelegt.

Zeitpunkt und Menge der Düngung sind so zu wählen, dass verfügbare oder verfügbar werdende Nährstoffe den Pflanzen zeitnah und in einer dem Bedarf der Pflanzen entsprechenden Menge zur Verfügung stehen.

Für ausgewiesene belastete Gebiete nach § 13 Abs. 2 DüV sind die Vorschriften der jeweiligen Landesregierungen zu beachten.

Anwendungsvorgaben

Die Ausbringung auf Grünland und mehrschnittigen Feldfutterflächen ist zulässig. Eine Anwendung bei Feldgemüse und Feldfutter darf nur vor dem Anbau mit anschließender Einarbeitung erfolgen. Keine Ausbringung auf wassergesättigten, überschwemmten, gefrorenen oder schneebedeckten Flächen. Die Ausbringung auf gefrorenem Boden nach § 5 Abs. 1 Satz 3 DüV ist zulässig (Voraussetzung: aufnahmefähiger Boden, weniger als 60 kg N/ges/ha, Pflanzendecke, keine Abschwemmung, Ausbringung zur Verhinderung von Bodenverdichtung).

Abstandsregelungen zu Gewässern sind zu berücksichtigen (§ 5 Abs. 2 und 3 DüV).

Bei der Aufbringung auf Feldgemüse- und Feldfutterflächen oberflächlich einarbeiten.

Figure 3: BGK certificate digestate pellets test report; original in German, page 3 of 3

Test certificate

RAL-GZ 246 PZ No.: 8559-151535-02

Pellets

RAL Quality Assurance Nawaro Fermentation Product Batch Inspection Page 1 of 3

Steinfurt plant (BGK no.: 8559) Batch: Pellets Sampling on 04.10.2017

Legal Provisions:

- Fertilizer Ordinance
- Organic NPK fertilizer
- Hygienically harmless (§ 5 Fertilizer Ordinance)

Rules and regulations:

- NawaRo fermentation product solid (Monitoring procedure RAL-GZ 246)
- External monitoring of the BGK
- Groundwater protection areas⁵⁾ (suitable for WSZ III)

Compliance with the respective standard is indicated by a check mark.

Goods declaration of RAL quality assurance¹⁾

Labeling

according to the Fertilizer

Organic NPK fertilizer 1.91-4.14-1.78 with trace nutrients using vegetable substances, animal by-products

1.91 % N total nitrogen 0.05 % N available nitrogen
4.14 % P₂O₅ Total phosphate
1.78 % K₂O Total potassium oxide 0.0197 % Zn Total zinc

Net mass and, if applicable, volume: see delivery bill

Distributor:
Bioenergie Steinfurt GmbH & Co KG
Hollich 81a
48565 Steinfurt

Starting materials:

Vegetable matter from agriculture (66%), liquid manure.

Storage Instructions:

Storage only in suitable and approved containers/plants, taking into account other legal regulations. Mix sufficiently before removal.

Instructions for use:

See Appendix LW for instructions on proper use. The recommendations of the official advice are to be considered with priority.

Application specifications:

When using this fertilizer, observe the blocking periods of the Fertilizer Ordinance during the winter months. [List Other Ingredients]

Other data:

Hygiene requirements tested and complied with.

Free from germinable seeds and sprouting plant parts

Fertilizer value²⁾ 38,81 €/t 26,16 €/m³
Humus value³⁾ 24,03 €/t 16,20 €/m³

Properties and ingredients

Ordinance in the fresh mass

	kg/t	kg/m ³
Total nitrogen (N)	19,20	12,94
Nitrogen CaCl ₂ -soluble (N)	0,54	0,36
Nitrogen organic (N)	18,66	12,58
Total phosphate (P ₂ O ₅)	41,40	27,91
Total potassium oxide (K ₂ O)	17,88	12,05
Magnesium oxide total (MgO)	21,64	14,59
Total sulfur (S)	3,39	2,28
Basic active substances (CaO)	20,04	13,51

pH value 7,2
Salinity 16 g/l
Organic matter 696 kg/t
Humus-C 141

kg/t
Bulk density 674

kg/m³
Dry matter 94 .1 %
Nitrogen from farm manure of animal origin 1 .5 kg/t FM

Product is subject to RAL quality assurance Nawaro fermentation product (RAL-GZ 246). The certificate was created electronically. It is valid without signature.

Federal Compost Quality Association e.V.
Carrier of the regular quality monitoring according to §11 Abs. 3 BioAbfV.

Cologne, 19.12.2017

1) binding goods declaration of RAL quality assurance at the time of delivery of the product. 2) According to current market value, determined via equivalent costs of mineral fertilization according to land trade prices (July - Sep. 2017) without VAT (0.63 €/kg N in the year of application (N-soluble plus 5% of N-organic); 0.63 € / kg P₂O₅; 0.57 €/kg K₂O; 0.08 €/kg CaO). 4) The value of humus-C is 0.17 €/kg humus-C (Calculated on the basis of a straw price of 72.50 €/t). 5) Reported on the basis of DVGW-BGK information dated 19.6.2013.

Figure 4: BGK certificate digestate pellets test report; machine translation in English, page 1 of 3

RAL-GZ 246

Investigation Report

PZ No.: 8559-151535-02

Pellets

Steinfurt
(BGK-No.: 8559)
Page 2 from 3Batch: Pellets
Sampling 04.10.2017
Test laboratory BGK No.: 46
Tgb no.: 17-156713-02

General data

Client: Bioenergie Steinfurt GmbH & Co. KG

Sampler: (BGK-No.: 674) Christian Winter
WESSLING Laboratorien GmbH

Testing laboratory: (BGK no.: 46) WESSLING GmbH
48341 Altenberge
Lab Responsible: Mr. Wellemann

Sampling date: Sample received by the laboratory: 04.10.2017
04.10.2017

Product sampled: NawaRo fermentation product solid 2

Production month: October
Batch: pellets

Process monitoring checked, not objected to

Input materials¹⁾

Share Designation

62% K1 Silage corn (whole plant) 17% D1 Cattle manure
17% D2 Pig manure 2.0% K4 Grain (grain)
2.0% K3 Cereals (whole plant)

Auxiliary materials

¹⁾ Feedstocks according to the list of permitted feedstocks for the production of quality-assured NawaRo fermentation products of the BGK (doc. 246-007-1)

Comment Sampler / -in:

Remark Testing laboratory:

Sampling and testing was carried out according to the BGK e.V. method book.

Altenberge, 19.12.2017

Analysis results

Unit	Parameter	Value
<u>Plant nutrients</u>		
Nitrogen, total (N)		2.04 % DM
Phosphate, total (P ₂₀₅)		4.40 % DM
Potassium oxide, total (K ₂ O)		1.90 % DM
Magnesium oxide, total (MgO)		2.30 % DM
Sulfur (S)		0.36 % DM
Copper (Cu)		51.0 mg/kg DM
Zinc (Zn)		210 mg/kg DM
Ammonium CaCl ₂ -soluble (NH ₄ -N)		350 mg/l FM
Nitrate CaCl ₂ -soluble (NO ₃ -N)		14 mg/l FM
<u>Soil improvement</u>		
Organic matter		74.0% DM
Basic active. Components (CaO)		2.13 % DM
<u>Physical parameters</u>		
Dry matter	94	Bulk density 674 g/l .1 % FM
Salinity	16	.0 g/l FM
pH value		7,2
Degree of fermentation		of fermentation 74
<u>(Organic acids)</u>		
Foreign matter > 2mm total	0	.00 % TM
- Formable plastics (film)		0.00 % TM
- Other foreign substances	0	.00 % TM
Degree of contamination (area total)		n.u.
<u>Biological parameters/hygiene</u>		
Germinable seeds / germinable plant parts	Plant parts	per l FM
Salmonella	not detectable	Odor inconspicuous
typical of the odorant type		
<u>Heavy metals</u>		
Lead (Pb)		> 1.00 mg/kg DM
Cadmium (Cd)		0.20 mg/kg DM
Chromium (Cr)		9.10 mg/kg DM
Nickel (Ni)		7.50 mg/kg DM
Mercury (Hg)		0.02 mg/kg DM
<u>Additional parameters</u>		
Stones >		10mm < 0,01 % TM

Figure 5: BGK certificate digestate pellets test report; machine translation in English, page 2 of 3

RAL-GZ 246

Application agriculture

Attachment LW to PZ-No.: 8559-151535-02

BGK no.: 8559

Pellets (NawaRo fermentation product solid 2)

Table 1: Data for fertilizer calculation
(data in fresh mass)

Ingredient	%	kg/t	kg/m ³
Total nitrogen (N)	1,92	19,2	12,9
Nitrogen soluble (N)	0,05	0,54	0,36
Nitrogen organic (N)	1,87	18,7	12,6
Total phosphate (P ₂ O ₅)	4,14	41,4	27,9
Total potassium oxide (K ₂ O)	1,79	17,9	12,1
Magnesium oxide total (MgO)	2,16	21,6	14,6
Bas. active. Components (CaO)	2,00	20,0	13,5
Organic substance	69,6	696	469
Humus-C	14,1	141	95,3

Conversion factors Application rate

The conversion factor from fresh mass (FM) to dry mass (TM) is 0.94 and from TM to FM 1.06. The conversion factor from volume (m³) to mass (t) is 0.67 and from t to m³ FM 1.48.

Table 2: Nitrogen utilization according to DüV
(minimum chargeability according to DüV, data in fresh mass)

Nitrogen (N)	%	kg/t	kg/m ³
	From P _{ges}		
Year of application ¹⁾	30	5,76	3,88
First subsequent year*	10	1,92	1,29

Phosphate (P O) ₂₅	%	kg/t	kg/m ³
	From P _{ges}		
Application in crop rotation ²⁾	100	41,4	27,9

*Consequential effect to be imputed according to § 4 para. 1 no. 5 DüV.

Table 3: Average application rates and fertilizer value

value (using the example of a three-tier crop rotation)	Application rate (FM)		Fertilizer value ^{3, 6)}	Humus value ⁴⁾
	t/ha	m ³ /ha	€/ha	€/ha
annual	1	2	56	35
in three years ²⁾	4	6	169	104

The table shows an example of application rates for supplying a three-tier crop rotation. The example is based on a medium supply level of the soil and an annual requirement of 60 kg/ha P O₂₅. In the present case, phosphate is limiting. The demand of the crop rotation (180 kg/ha P O₂₅) can be met with 4 t or 6 m³/ha of fermentation product.

1) Determined content of available nitrogen, but at least 30% of total N (DüV Annex 3). 2) In case of fertilization for the entire crop rotation (basic fertilization), the annual application rates can be summed up for a demand coverage of 3 years. 3) According to current market value, determined via equivalent costs of mineral fertilization according to average land trade prices (July - Sep. 2017) without VAT (0.63 €/kg N-allowable, 0.63 €/kg P O₂₅, 0.57 €/kg K₂O, 0.08 €/kg CaO). 4) The value of humus-C is 0.17 €/kg humus-C (Calculated on the basis of a straw price of 72.50 €/t). 5) Retrieved from www.kompost.de. 6) Creditable nitrogen in the year of application (N-soluble plus 5% of N-organic).

Accounting for nutrients and humus

Nitrogen in the fermentation product is present in mineral and organically bound form. Table 2 shows the creditability according to the German Fertilizer Ordinance (DüV).

Phosphate, potassium oxide, magnesium oxide and basic active substances are 100% creditable in the crop rotation. Humus-C is the humus-reproduction carbon (humus-C) that can be credited within the framework of the humus balance according to VDLUFA.

Information according to fertilizer ordinance

According to DüV it is a fertilizer

- With essential nutrient content
(according to § 2, No. 11 DüV, >1.5 % N or >0.5 % P O₂₅ i.d.)

- With substantial content of nitrogen
(according to § 2 No. 11 DüV >1.5% N)

The fermentation product is subject to the blocking period in the winter months according to § 6 para. 8 DüV. (usually arable land: harvest of the last main crop by 31 January, grassland: 1 November to 31 January). Exceptions according to § 6 para. 9 DüV are possible.

The nutrient comparison is based on the total nitrogen and phosphate contents.

The timing and amount of fertilizer application shall be such that available or becoming available nutrients are available to the plants in a timely manner and in amounts appropriate to the plants' needs.

For designated polluted areas according to § 13 para. 2 DüV, the regulations of the respective state governments must be observed.

Application specifications

Application to grassland and multi-cut field forage areas is permitted. Application to field vegetables and field forage may only be made prior to cultivation with subsequent incorporation. No application on waterlogged, flooded, frozen or snow-covered land. Application on frozen soil after

§ 5 para. 1 sentence 3 DüV is permissible (prerequisite: absorbent soil, less than 60 kg Nges/ha, plant cover, no run-off, application to prevent soil compaction). Distance regulations to water bodies must be taken into account (§ 5 para. 2 and 3 DüV).

When applying to field vegetable and forage areas, incorporate superficially.

Figure 6: BGK certificate digestate pellets test report; machine translation in English, page 3 of 3

ANNEX II – TCR30 V69 digestate pellets test report

Eurofins Umwelt Ost GmbH - Lindenstraße 11 - Gewerbegebiet Freiberg Ost -
D-09627 Bobritzsch-Hilbersdorf

**Fraunhofer Institut
UMSICHT
An der Maxhütte 1
92237 Sulzbach-Rosenberg**

Title : **Extract from (Batch): AR-23-FR-046782-01 (12343397)**

Test report number : **EX-23-FR-002730-01**

Project name : **Funded ED Proj. 101083780 NET-Fuels**

Number of samples : **1**

Sample type: **sewage sludge**

Date of sample taking : **2023-08-23**

Sample Taker: **not specified, sample(s) were delivered to lab**

Sample reception date : **2023-10-02**

Sample processing time : **2023-10-02 - 2023-10-09**

Comment: **The purchase is funded by the European commission under grant agreement Project 101083780 -- NET-Fuels**

The test results solely refer to the analysed test specimen. Unless the sampling was done by our laboratory or in our sub-order the responsibility for the correctness of the sampling is disclaimed. This analytical report is electronically signed and may only be further published completely and unchanged. Extracts or changes require the authorisation of the EUROFINS UMWELT in each individual case.

Our General Terms & Conditions of Sale (GTCS) are applicable, as far as no specific agreements do exist. The GTCS are available on <http://www.eurofins.de/umwelt/avb.aspx>.

Accredited test laboratory according to DIN EN ISO/IEC 17025:2018 DAkkS notification under the DAkkS German Accreditation System for Testing. The laboratory is according (D-PL-14081-01-00) accredited.

Ulrich Erler
Analytical Service Manager

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Digitally signed 10/30/2023
Ralf Dedow
Analytical Service Manager

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GF: Axel Ulbricht, Matthias Prauser
Amtsgericht Jena HRB 202596
USt.-ID.Nr. DE 151 28 1997

Bankverbindung: UniCredit Bank AG
BLZ 207 300 17
Kto 7000000550
IBAN DE07 2073 0017 7000 0005 50
BIC/SWIFT HYVEDEMM17

Figure 7: TCR30 V69 digestate pellets test report, page 1 of 3

				Description	TCR30-69_Gärrest Pellets	
				Date and time of sample taking	2023-08-23	
				Sample number	123154518	
Parameter	Lab	Accr.	Method	LOQ	Unit	
Physico-chemical parameters from the original substance						
Bulk density	FR	F5	Methodenbuch der BGK e.V.: 9/2006, Kap. II, A 4	10	g/l	700
Moisture	FR	F5	DIN EN 12880 (S2a): 2001-02	0.1	Ma.-% Raw Product	12.7
gross calorific value (q _o ,V)	FR	F5	DIN EN 15170: 2009-05	0.20	MJ/kg Raw Product	15.06 ¹⁾
gross calorific value (q _o ,V)	FR	F5	DIN EN 15170: 2009-05	0.20	MJ/kg dw	17.25 ¹⁾
net calorific value (q _p ,net)	FR	F5	DIN EN 15170: 2009-05	0.20	MJ/kg Raw Product	13.87 ²⁾
net calorific value (q _p ,net)	FR	F5	DIN EN 15170: 2009-05	0.20	MJ/kg dw	16.23 ²⁾
net calorific value (q _u ,V)	FR	F5	DIN EN 15170: 2009-05	0.20	MJ/kg Raw Product	13.94 ³⁾
net calorific value (q _u ,V)	FR	F5	DIN EN 15170: 2009-05	0.20	MJ/kg dw	16.29 ³⁾
Inorganic sum parameters from the original substance						
Ash content (815°C)	FR	F5	DIN 51719: 1997-07	0.1	Ma.-% Raw Product	12.9
Ash content (815°C)	FR	F5	DIN 51719: 1997-07	0.1	% (w/w) dm	14.7
Elements from the original substance						
Carbon	FR	F5	DIN 51732: 2014-07	0.2	Ma.-% Raw Product	37.5
Carbon	FR	F5	DIN 51732: 2014-07	0.2	% (w/w) dm	42.9
Hydrogen	FR	F5	DIN 51732: 2014-07	0.10	Ma.-% Raw Product	4.06
Hydrogen	FR	F5	DIN 51732: 2014-07	0.10	% (w/w) dm	4.65
Total nitrogen	FR	F5	DIN 51732: 2014-07	0.05	Ma.-% Raw Product	1.61
Total nitrogen	FR	F5	DIN 51732: 2014-07	0.05	% (w/w) dm	1.84
Sulphur (S), total	FR	F5	DIN 51724-3: 2012-07	0.03	Ma.-% Raw Product	0.45
Sulphur (S), total	FR	F5	DIN 51724-3: 2012-07	0.03	% (w/w) dm	0.51
Oxygen	FR	F5	DIN 51733: 2016-04		Ma.-% Raw Product	30.9
Oxygen	FR	F5	DIN 51733: 2016-04		% (w/w) dm	35.3
Organic sum parameters from the original substance						
Volatile Compounds	FR	F5	DIN 51720: 2001-03	0.2	Ma.-% Raw Product	56.8
Volatile Compounds	FR	F5	DIN 51720: 2001-03	0.2	% (w/w) dm	65.0
Fixed carbon	FR	F5	DIN 51734: 2008-12		Ma.-% Raw Product	17.7
Fixed carbon	FR	F5	DIN 51734: 2008-12		% (w/w) dm	20.3
Special analyses						
Plausibility check	FR					OK

Figure 8: TCR30 V69 digestate pellets test report, page 2 of 3

“TCR30-69_Gärrest pellets” refers to TCR30 V69 digestate pellets.

Umwelt

Report number : EX-23-FR-002730-01

Page 3 of 3

Explanations

LOQ - Limit of quantification

Lab - Abbreviation of the performing laboratory

Accr. - Abbreviation of the accreditation of the performing laboratory

Comments for results

¹⁾ (q_o, V) gross calorific value at constant volume

²⁾ (q_p, net) net calorific value at constant pressure

³⁾ (q_u, V) net calorific value at constant volume

The parameters identified by FR have been performed by the laboratory Eurofins Umwelt Ost GmbH (Lindenstraße 11, Gewerbegebiet Freiberg Ost, Bobritzsch-Hilbersdorf). The accreditation code F5 identifies the parameters accredited according to DIN EN ISO/IEC 17025:2018 DAkkS D-PL-14081-01-00 .

Figure 9: TCR30 V69 digestate pellets test report, page 3 of 3

ANNEX III – TCR30 V70 wine prunings and TCR30 V72 hops extraction residues pellets report

Umwelt

Report number : EX-23-FR-002731-01

Page 1 of 3

Eurofins Umwelt Ost GmbH - Lindenstraße 11 - Gewerbegebiet Freiberg Ost -
D-09627 Bobritzsch-Hilbersdorf

**Fraunhofer Institut
UMSICHT
An der Maxhütte 1
92237 Sulzbach-Rosenberg**

Title : **Extract from (Batch): AR-23-FR-047940-01 (12343393)**
Test report number : **EX-23-FR-002731-01**

Project name : **Funded EC Proj. 101083780 NET-Fuels**

Number of samples : **2**
Sample type: **solid biofuel**
Date of sample taking : **2023-08-23, 2023-09-28**
Sample Taker: **not specified, sample(s) were delivered to lab**

Sample reception date : **2023-10-02**
Sample processing time : **2023-10-02 - 2023-10-10**

Comment: **The purchase is funded by the European commission under grant agreement Project 101083780 -- NET-Fuels**

The test results solely refer to the analysed test specimen. Unless the sampling was done by our laboratory or in our sub-order the responsibility for the correctness of the sampling is disclaimed. This analytical report is electronically signed and may only be further published completely and unchanged. Extracts or changes require the authorisation of the EUROFINS UMWELT in each individual case.

Our General Terms & Conditions of Sale (GTCS) are applicable, as far as no specific agreements do exist. The GTCS are available on <http://www.eurofins.de/umwelt/avb.aspx>.

Accredited test laboratory according to DIN EN ISO/IEC 17025:2018 DAkkS notification under the DAkkS German Accreditation System for Testing. The laboratory is according (D-PL-14081-01-00) accredited.

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Bankverbindung: UniCredit Bank AG
BLZ 207 300 17
Kto 7000000550
IBAN DE07 2073 0017 7000 0005 50
BIC/SWIFT HYVEDEMM17

Figure 10: TCR30 V70 wine prunings and TCR30 V72 hops extraction residues pellets report, page 1 of 3

				Description		TCR-30-70_Rebschnitt Pellets	
				Date and time of sample taking		2023-08-23	
				Sample number		123154502	
Parameter	Lab	Accr.	Method	LOQ	Unit	ar	db
Physico-chemical parameters from the original substance							
Bulk density	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 17828: 2016-05		kg/m ³	680	-
Moisture	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 18134-2: 2017-05	0.1	% (w/w)	7.9	-
Gross calorific value (qV,gr)	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 18125: 2017-08	200	kJ/kg	17500 ¹⁾	19000 ¹⁾
Net calorific value (qp,net)	FR	F5	berechnet nach DIN EN ISO 18125: 2017-08	200	kJ/kg	16200 ²⁾	17800 ²⁾
Inorganic sum parameters from the original substance							
Ash content (550°C)	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 18122: 2016-03	0.1	% (w/w)	4.1	4.5
Elements from the original substance							
Carbon	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 16948: 2015-09	0.2	% (w/w)	44.1	47.9
Hydrogen	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 16948: 2015-09	0.1	% (w/w)	5.1	5.5
Nitrogen	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 16948: 2015-09	0.05	% (w/w)	0.81	0.88
Sulphur	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 16994: 2016-12	0.005	% (w/w)	0.049	0.053
Oxygen	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 16993: 2016-11		% (w/w)	37.9	41.2
Organic sum parameters from the original substance							
Loss on ignition at 550°C	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 18122: 2016-03	0.1	% (w/w)	88.0	95.5
Volatile Compounds	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 18123: 2016-03	0.2	% (w/w)	70.1	76.1
Fixed carbon	FR	F5	DIN 51734: 2008-12		% (w/w)	17.9	19.5
Special analyses							
Plausibility check	FR					OK	-

Figure 11: TCR30 V70 wine prunings and TCR30 V72 hops extraction residues pellets report, page 2 of 3

“TCR-30-70_Rebschnitt Pellets” refers to TCR30 V70 wine prunings pellets.

“TCR-30-XX_Hopfentreber Pellets” refers to TCR 30 V72 hops extraction residues pellets.

				Description		TCR-30-XX_Hopfentre-ber Pellets	
				Date and time of sample taking		2023-09-28	
				Sample number		123154503	
Parameter	Lab	Accr.	Method	LOQ	Unit	ar	db
Physico-chemical parameters from the original substance							
Bulk density	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 17828: 2016-05		kg/m ³	611	-
Moisture	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 18134-2: 2017-05	0.1	% (w/w)	11.2	-
Gross calorific value (qV,gr)	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 18125: 2017-08	200	kJ/kg	16300 ¹⁾	18300 ¹⁾
Net calorific value (qp,net)	FR	F5	berechnet nach DIN EN ISO 18125: 2017-08	200	kJ/kg	15000 ²⁾	17200 ²⁾
Inorganic sum parameters from the original substance							
Ash content (550°C)	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 18122: 2016-03	0.1	% (w/w)	8.9	10.1
Elements from the original substance							
Carbon	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 16948: 2015-09	0.2	% (w/w)	40.9	46.1
Hydrogen	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 16948: 2015-09	0.1	% (w/w)	4.7	5.3
Nitrogen	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 16948: 2015-09	0.05	% (w/w)	3.62	4.08
Sulphur	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 16994: 2016-12	0.005	% (w/w)	0.225	0.254
Oxygen	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 16993: 2016-11		% (w/w)	30.4	34.2
Organic sum parameters from the original substance							
Loss on ignition at 550°C	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 18122: 2016-03	0.1	% (w/w)	79.9	89.9
Volatile Compounds	FR	F5	DIN EN ISO 18123: 2016-03	0.2	% (w/w)	62.7	70.7
Fixed carbon	FR	F5	DIN 51734: 2008-12		% (w/w)	17.1	19.3
Special analyses							
Plausibility check	FR					OK	-

Explanations

LOQ - Limit of quantification

ar - as received

db - dry basis

Lab - Abbreviation of the performing laboratory

Accr. - Abbreviation of the accreditation of the performing laboratory

Comments for results

¹⁾ (qV, gr) gross calorific value at constant volume

²⁾ (qp, net) net calorific value at constant pressure

The parameters identified by FR have been performed by the laboratory Eurofins Umwelt Ost GmbH (Lindenstraße 11, Gewerbegebiet Freiberg Ost, Bobritzsch-Hilbersdorf). The accreditation code F5 identifies the parameters accredited according to DIN EN ISO/IEC 17025:2018 DAkkS D-PL-14081-01-00 .

Figure 12: TCR30 V70 wine prunings and TCR30 V72 hops extraction residues pellets report, page 3 of 3

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DIN EN ISO 18123:2016-03, Solid biofuels - Determination of the content of volatile matter

DIN EN ISO 18125:2017-08, Solid biofuels - Determination of calorific value

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DIN EN ISO 18134-3:2023-09, Solid biofuels - Determination of moisture content - Part 3: Moisture in general analysis sample

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DIN 51720: 2001-03, Testing of solid fuels - Determination of volatile matter content

DIN 51724-3:2012-07, Solid mineral fuels - Determination of sulfur content - Part 3: Instrumental methods

DIN 51732: 2014-07, Testing of solid mineral fuels - Determination of total carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen - Instrumental methods

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